

SHORT NOTES

Condensation Reaction of Diphenic Anhydride with Hydrazines

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Condensation of ethyl diphenate with hydrazine hydrate in a sealed tube gave diphenic acid dihydrazide¹, which on oxidation with potassium ferricyanide afforded diphenhydrazide² (I) as a by-product. Phthalic anhydride and phthalimide react with appropriate hydrazines to give phthalhydrazide and *N*-aminophthalimides³. It is now found that when diphenic anhydride is treated with hydrazine hydrate under varied conditions, *N*-aminodiphenimide (II) is obtained as the major product. Thus, reaction of diphenic anhydride with hydrazine hydrate in methanol gives *N*-aminodiphenimide in 20% yield. Heating diphenic anhydride with hydrazine hydrate on a steam bath gives better yield of the same product together with a coloured compound which cannot be isolated in a crystalline condition.

Diazotization of *N*-aminodiphenimide gives *N*-hydroxydiphenimide (III). Phenylhydrazine reacts with diphenic anhydride to furnish mainly *N*-phenyl-diphenhydrazide (IV) which is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate, soluble in dilute alkali and reprecipitated unchanged with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. Its infrared spectrum shows =NH stretching

1. Kalb and Gross, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 736.
2. Borsche, Müller and Bodenstern, *Ann.*, 1929, 475, 122.
3. Drew and Peerman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 36.

frequency at 3450 cm.^{-1} and the $=\text{CO}$ at 1650 cm.^{-1} of the amide. M.P.s are uncorrected. Analyses were carried out by Alfred Bernhardt, Max-Planck Institute, Mulheim, Ruhr, Germany. Infrared spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord Model 137E spectrophotometer in KBr wafers.

N-Aminodiphenimide.—(a) Diphenic anhydride (3 g.) (obtained by heating diphenic acid in acetic anhydride and phosphoric acid for 2 hrs., m.p. 217°) was heated with 98% hydrazine hydrate (3 c.c.) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was extracted with hot benzene. Evaporation of the benzene solution gave yellow amorphous non-crystallisable compound insoluble in sodium bicarbonate or sodium hydroxide solution. The residue after extraction with benzene was crystallised from water and afforded *N*-aminodiphenimide in white needles (1.5 g., 48%), m.p. $180-181^\circ$ (Found: C, 70.1; H, 4.6; N, 11.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 70.5; H, 4.2; N, 11.7%).

(b) A solution of diphenic anhydride (0.5 g.) in methanol (10 c.c.) was heated with 98% hydrazine hydrate (0.5 c.c.) for 2 hrs. on a water bath. On evaporation, the product solidified on treatment with light petroleum (b.p. $100-120^\circ$) and crystallised from water to yield *N*-aminodiphenimide in white needles (1.5 g., 20%) m.p. $180-181^\circ$.

N-Hydroxydiphenimide.—An ice cold 10% aqueous solution of NaNO_2 (5 c.c.) was added slowly with stirring to a solution of *N*-aminodiphenimide (0.2 g.) in 2N HCl Acid (10 c.c.) cooled in ice. The mixture was gently heated on a water bath. Crystallisation of the product from absolute alcohol gave *N*-hydroxydiphenimide in yellow needles (0.1 g., 52%), m.p. $286-287^\circ$. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 4.1; N, 5.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: C, 70.2; H, 3.8; N, 5.8%).

N-Phenyl-diphenhydrazide.—Phenyl hydrazine (6 c.c.) was added to diphenic anhydride (3 g.) and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 3 hrs. The product on cooling and treatment with ether afforded a solid soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide from which solution it was precipitated unchanged by addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. Crystallisation of the compound from aqueous ethanol gave *N*-phenyl-diphenhydrazide in yellow needles m.p. $206-208^\circ$. (3.5 g., 83%). (Found: C, 76.1; H, 4.6; N, 8.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 76.4; H, 4.5; N, 8.8%).